

Giant maxillary radicular cyst: Case report

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Abstract

Introduction: Radicular cysts are the most common odontogenic cysts, usually small and asymptomatic, but occasionally enlarge enough to distort facial contours and obstruct the nasal airway.

Case report: A 35-year-old man presented with progressive right maxillary swelling and nasal obstruction. Examination showed a firm bony mass effacing the nasolabial and palpebro-jugal folds and deforming the right nostril threshold. CT revealed a well-defined, expansile intramaxillary cyst extending into both nasal cavities and the right orbital floor without aggressive features. Histopathology confirmed a radicular cyst. The lesion was excised via a wide paralateronasal Weber–Ferguson approach with anterior maxillary osteotomy. Careful dissection along the orbital floor allowed complete enucleation without the need for reconstruction. Recovery was uneventful; at six months the patient had restored jugal projection and improved bilateral nasal airflow.

Discussion: While most radicular cysts are managed conservatively, very large lesions risk displacement of the nasal cavity and orbit and may require open approaches for safe extraction. This case illustrates indications for radical access, key operative steps, and favourable functional and aesthetic outcomes after complete enucleation.

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Introduction

Radicular (periapical) cysts arise from inflammatory stimulation of epithelial rests of Malassez and account for the majority of odontogenic cysts, particularly in the maxilla¹⁻³. Most are incidental findings, radiographically appearing as well-circumscribed periapical radiolucencies²⁻⁴. Although typically <1 cm, neglected lesions may expand, thin cortical bone, and encroach on the nasal cavity or orbit.^{1,6-8} Management ranges from endodontic treatment and decompression to enucleation; recurrence is uncommon with complete removal^{2-4,9}. We report a giant maxillary radicular cyst requiring open resection via a Weber–Ferguson approach.

Case report

A 35-year-old man presented with six months of progressive right facial swelling and nasal blockage. Extra-oral examination revealed a firm, non-tender jugal mass confluent with the maxilla, effacing the right

nasolabial and palpebro-jugal folds and distorting the nostril threshold. Anterior rhinoscopy showed filling of the right nasal fossa, septal deviation, and reduced bilateral airflow.

Non-contrast CT demonstrated a large, well-defined, unilocular expansile lesion centred in the right maxilla, remodelling the walls, extending into both nasal cavities and abutting the floor of the right orbit, with no periosteal reaction or soft-tissue invasion (Figure 1). An intra-oral biopsy confirmed a radicular cyst lined by non-keratinised stratified squamous epithelium with chronic inflammatory infiltrate.

Under general anaesthesia, a wide paralateronasal Weber–Ferguson incision with palpebro-jugal extension was performed. An anterior maxillary osteotomy exposed a tense cyst wall. Dissection proceeded circumferentially; along the orbital floor a cottonoid-assisted, blunt technique preserved periorbital structures. The cyst was completely enucleated intact. Given preserved bony support and

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Figure 1. (a) Coronal CT section showing superior extension of the cyst to the orbital floor with evident bone remodelling. (b) Axial CT view demonstrating complete obliteration of both nasal fossae and posterior extension into the nasopharynx, with cortical expansion. (c) Sagittal CT section illustrating the full anteroposterior extent of the cystic lesion.

Figure 2. (a) Right paralateronasal (Weber–Ferguson) incision revealing outward expansion of the anterior maxillary wall due to the underlying cyst. (b) Osteotomy of the anterior maxillary wall performed to access the intramaxillary cystic cavity.

stable globe position, orbital floor reconstruction was not required. Haemostasis was secured and layered closure achieved with 4-0 Vicryl and 5-0 nylon (Figure 2).

Post-operative recovery was uneventful. Histopathology confirmed a radicular cyst. At six-month review, facial symmetry improved, nasal airflow was restored bilaterally, and there was no clinical or radiological evidence of recurrence.

Discussion

Radicular cysts result from cystic degeneration of apical granulomas following pulp necrosis and chronic periapical inflammation^{1-3,6}. They predominantly affect permanent maxillary teeth and are often asymptomatic until expansion causes cosmetic deformity, nasal obstruction, dental mobility, or secondary infection^{2,7,8}. Imaging typically shows a unilocular radiolucency with corticated borders related to a non-vital tooth; CT/CBCT delineates anatomical relationships and surgical corridors^{2,3,6}.

Small and moderate lesions often respond to endodontic therapy, decompression/marsupialisation, or intra-oral enucleation, with low recurrence when the cyst lining is completely removed^{2-4,9}. However, “giant” cysts can exceed 5 cm, displace the nasal cavity and orbit, and thin the anterior and medial maxillary walls, increasing the risk of fracture or orbital breach during extraction^{1,6-8}. In such cases, external access (e.g., Weber–Ferguson) with planned osteotomy affords perpendicular control, safe dissection along the orbital floor, and en-bloc removal. Our case supports this strategy: open access enabled controlled mobilisation, avoided orbital injury, and obviated reconstruction.

Key operative principles include gentle, subperiosteal elevation; preservation of neurovascular bundles; and blunt dissection where the cyst abuts the orbit. Where the orbital floor is markedly thinned or dehiscent, immediate reconstruction may be indicated; in our patient, intact periorbita and stable globe allowed omission of grafting.

Limitations of this report include the single-case design and six-month follow-up. Nonetheless, it highlights scenarios where conservative intra-oral approaches are unsafe and documents good functional and aesthetic outcomes after radical access and complete enucleation.

Giant maxillary radicular cysts can cause marked facial deformity and nasal obstruction. Cross-sectional imaging guides access. When expansion threatens the orbit or nasal cavity, a Weber–Ferguson approach with maxillary osteotomy permits safe, complete excision and rapid recovery, with low recurrence when the lining is removed in toto^{2-4,9}.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Patient consent: Written informed consent was obtained for publication and images.

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